

Development of ANN algorithms for forecasting Fresnel thermal power production

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ABSTRACT

Renewable energy production technologies are indispensable to the development of a clean and energy efficient built environment. Being dependent on climatic parameters, renewable energy production may vary causing a mismatch between energy demand and available production. Therefore, forecasting of renewable energy production allows the design and implementation of management schedules depending on expected production, thus assisting towards a more efficient and secure operation. The application of artificial neural networks (ANN) has been proved effective towards this aim. The present work is investigating the application of ANN for production forecasting of a concentrated solar power (CSP) fresnel system. The fresnel system production is optimum under clear skies and peak direct solar radiation. The system under investigation is connected to a thermal storage and its production is used to cover the heating/cooling loads of a building. The prediction can be used for scheduling the times that the system focalizes and de-focalizes for optimizing energy production and storage. The present work is relevant to researchers, engineers and developers of renewable energy production technologies that work on optimization of energy production and management. This work can be extended to smart grid energy management.

Keywords

CSP, fresnel, ANN, forecasting.

1. INTRODUCTION

The built environment constitutes the greatest component of energy consumption and one that is also dependent on non-renewable sources [1]. On the way to developing a clean and energy efficient built environment, building energy design as well as energy production and distribution to buildings has been put under new perspective where renewable energy sources (RES) can play a key role. The concepts of zero energy buildings as well as smart energy grids both assume RES integration [1], [2], [3], [4].

Renewables can be an unpredictable source of energy since their production can be affected by climatic variations. Specifically for

the case smart grids, RES integration presents challenges that need to be overcome for achieving efficient energy management and stability of the energy grid [3], [5]. Forecasting of renewable energy production can be an invaluable tool towards efficient energy and cost efficient management [6].

Artificial intelligence models have been recognized in literature as a reliable forecasting method [7], [8]. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are artificial intelligence models that have been widely used for forecasting with high accuracy and have been extensively used for short-term prediction [7], [8], [9], [10].

In [9] short-term load forecasting is studied with the aim to control charge and discharge of an electrical storage that is connected to a smart-grid with high PV integration. The proposed methods achieve accurate predictions that support efficient operation of the storage and management of the smart-grid.

Load forecasting with the aim to achieve cost optimum operation of a smart micro-grid through optimum management of an electric storage that is connected to the grid is studied in [11]. The forecasted demand and production values are used as inputs of a genetic algorithm that decides the best management strategy.

A feed forward artificial neural network is proposed in [10] for predicting the load demand of a power grid. The proposed algorithm is able to achieve a highly accurate prediction that can support energy and cost efficient management of the grid.

In [12], an ANN has been developed for forecasting 24 hours ahead the excess power production from renewables in a micro-grid. The prediction can be used for charging a thermal storage and therefore allowing optimum utilization of the energy produced from the RES of the micro-grid.

In the present work, 24h forecasting of the thermal power production of a fresnel system is investigated with the aim to achieve efficient management of the system and cover power production intermittencies through controlled charge and discharge of a thermal storage.

2. CASE STUDY

2.1 Concentrated Solar Power

Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) technologies convert direct solar radiation into thermal energy, which can then be transformed into electricity through a thermodynamic cycle [13]. As recent research developments and worldwide installations have demonstrated, CSP are promising technologies for power generation [14]. Through 4 pilot installations, the application of concentrated solar power technologies in small and middle scale installations with the possibility of multi-generation, has been demonstrated [15].

As identified in [14], four types of CSP plants have been realized around the world:

- Solar Parabolic Dishes (SPD)
- Parabolic Trough Collectors (PTC)
- Solar Power Tower (SPT)
- Linear Fresnel Reflectors (LFR)

PTC has been the most widely implemented CSP technology [14]. However LFR is also a promising technology that presents certain advantages compared to the PTC. It requires less capital investment, it has a simpler and compact design that occupies less land and is constructed of less expensive components especially as far as the mirrors and tracking system are considered [16].

2.2 FRESCO system

In the present work the FRESCO system that has been developed by IDEA srl is considered as the basis for the investigation. The FRESCO system is based on Linear Fresnel Collector CSP technology.

One of the system's advantages is its compact and light structure that makes it suitable for installation on flat roofs. Such is the case of the installation on the Novel Tehnologies Laboratory (NTL) in Cyprus (Figure 1). Apart from being a showcase for other similar installations, the pilot also has demonstrated the integration of solar cooling in an existing HVAC installation and consequent reduction of electricity and fossil fuel use [17].

Figure 1. The FRESCO system installation on the NTL roof [18]

The FRESCO system is composed of:

- Linear Fresnel Reflectors
- Buffer storage
- Thermal Storage
- ORC (optional)

Its operation principle is based on the concentration of solar rays, by means of properly oriented high reflectivity mirrors, on a receiver tube in which a high temperature heat transfer fluid flows. The mirrors track the position of the sun throughout the day. The heated fluid when exiting the tube is stored into a short-term buffer storage that allows to control production instabilities. Eventually, the produced thermal energy is collected at about 270°C and is stored inside a storage tank which can

- (i) either heat buildings directly
- (ii) or serve chillers for thermal energy transformation into cooling energy.

Moreover, the system can be connected to an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) unit so as to produce electricity [19].

The coupling of flat PV panels on the reverse side of the mirrors can introduce a very high flexibility in energy generation. When the direct solar irradiation is low (e.g. cloudy days) the mirrors are reverse and diffuse solar radiation is used to produce electricity by PV panels, thus increasing the contribution of the FRESCO production on electricity saving [18].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset preparation

The data that have been used for forecasting the thermal power production of FRESCO have been collected from the installation of the solar field in Palermo (Figure 2).

Figure 2. General plan of the solar field in Palermo with three parallel rows of linear fresnel collectors [19]

The data are measured per five seconds and include the following:

- T (in): temperature of the oil at the beginning of the absorption pipe
- T (out): temperature of the oil at the end of the absorption pipe
- Q: flow of the oil
- DNI: Direct normal irradiance
- T (amb.): Ambient air temperature
- Wind speed

From the above measured data are calculated:

- The focalization/defocalization state of the mirrors
- The thermal power of the system
- The efficiency of the system

For the creation of the dataset that was used for the prediction, the measured values per minute were used and the intermediate values per second were filtered out.

Furthermore, if the value of Q was below 0.1, this was an indication that the system was not operating. Thus, the days that $Q < 0.1$ during operating hours of the system, were removed from the dataset. Among these days were also the weekends and holidays during which the system was not working.

Two datasets were collected eventually:

1. Dataset containing 40 days of May-June-July 2017 (19 days of May, 8 days from June and 13 days of July)
2. Dataset containing 32 days of September-October-November (14 days of September, 16 days of October, 2 days of November)

3.2 Forecasting using Neural Network

The forecasting of the thermal power production was the subject of the present work. The thermal power forecasting was solved as a non-linear autoregressive problem. Past values of thermal production as well as past values of the parameters that are used for the calculation of and affect the thermal power production were used for forecasting the thermal power (Table 1) in 24h horizon.

Table 1. Input and target data used for prediction

Inputs	Target	Output
day of week	thermal power	thermal power
time of day		
temperature of the oil at the beginning of the absorption pipe		

temperature of the oil at the end of the absorption pipe		
flow of the oil		
DNI		
Ambient air temperature		
Wind speed		

In previous work for the excess power production of the Leaf lab micro-grid a neural network structure with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays gave the best prediction results and the Lavenberg-Marquardt algorithm was used for training the network [12]. This configuration was used in the present case study as well. Moreover, 70% of the input data were used for training the neural network, 15% for validating and 15% for testing the prediction. The Neural Network Toolbox of Matlab was employed for this process.

The result of this process is the regression R that is achieved from training, validating and testing the ANN. A regression value close to 1 indicates that the network configuration is effective in providing highly accurate forecasts. However, a comparison of the actual with the predicted values could give a deeper insight in the forecasting results that are achieved. Following, the code script of Matlab that was used for training, validating and testing the network was accessed and edited so as to produce the predicted values and plot them along the actual values.

4. RESULTS

4.1 ANN training

The training of the network with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays for both data series resulted in satisfactory prediction results achieving a good regression.

The first dataset containing data form May, June and July 2017 resulted in a good overall regression $R=0.977$, Figure 3.

Figure 3. Regression results for the dataset May-July 2017

Figure 4. Regression results for the dataset September-November 2017

4.2 Comparison of predicted and actual values

Obtaining a good regression is indicative that reliable forecasting can be achieved. However, dispersion of data away from the regression line is noticeable, especially in Figure 3. Therefore, comparison of the actual to the predicted values gave a deeper insight in evaluating the developed ANN.

In Figure 5 are illustrated the actual thermal power data and the predicted values for the dataset May-July.

Figure 5. Actual thermal power (blue) plotted against predicted thermal power (red), ANN with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays, May-June dataset

In Figure 6 one day from the period May-July is plotted.

Figure 6. Actual thermal power (blue) plotted against predicted thermal power (red), ANN with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays, 1 day from May-June dataset

In Figure 7 are illustrated the actual thermal power data and the predicted values for the dataset September-November.

Figure 7. Actual thermal power (blue) plotted against predicted thermal power (red), ANN with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays, September-November dataset

In Figure 8 one day from the period May-July is plotted.

Figure 8. Actual thermal power (blue) plotted against predicted thermal power (red), ANN with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays, 1 day of September-November dataset

4.3 Discussion of results

The results indicate that the forecasted values follow closely the actual values of thermal power. However, errors are also visible. For that purpose the errors were evaluated by calculating the Mean Bias Error (MBE) and the root mean square error (RMSE).

Alternative ANN structures were also considered in order to evaluate the influence of the hidden neurons and the delays in the forecasting accuracy of the ANN, Table 2.

Table 2. Alternative ANN structures

	ANN1	ANN2	ANN3	ANN4	ANN5
delays	1	1	2	2	5
hidden neurons	10	30	10	30	30

In Table 3 and Table 4 are presented the MBE and RMSE as well as the regression value R for the various ANN considered. The second dataset presents better results, but this is the smaller dataset, therefore it is expected that errors will be less than the errors that appear in a larger and thus more representative dataset.

Table 3. Evaluation of ANN forecasting accuracy (dataset May-July)

	ANN1	ANN2	ANN3	ANN4	ANN5
MBE	0.03	0.029	0.09	0.04	0.018
RMSE	3.09	3.05	2.60	2.50	2.59
R	0.963	0.964	0.973	0.974	0.977

Table 4. Evaluation of ANN forecasting accuracy (dataset September-November)

	ANN1	ANN2	ANN3	ANN4	ANN5
MBE	-0.013	-0.018	0.049	0.049	0.0127
RMSE	1.71	1.70	1.60	1.60	1.57
R	0.982	0.982	0.983	0.984	0.986

Overall good R values and RMSE values are achieved with all ANN structures. It is also observed that increasing the number of delays improves the performance of the network, whereas increasing the numbers of neurons does not change the performance of the network. It can be concluded that a simple structure network with 10 hidden neurons and 2 delays can produce results as good as the network with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays, for the considered forecasting problem.

In Figure 9 are illustrated the actual thermal power data and the predicted values for the dataset May-July for the ANN structure with 10 hidden neurons and 2 delays.

Figure 9. Actual thermal power (blue) plotted against predicted thermal power (red), ANN with 10 hidden neurons and 2 delays, May-July dataset

In Figure 10 one day from the period May-July is plotted for the ANN with 10 hidden neurons and 2 delays.

Figure 10. Actual thermal power (blue) plotted against predicted thermal power (red), ANN with 10 hidden neurons and 2 delays, 1 day from May-July dataset.

One major parameter that affects the thermal power of the network but cannot be measured or considered in the forecasting problem is the dust. In addition to dust, shadowing and blocking effects between mirrors as well as solar tracking accuracy can affect the thermal power production. Therefore, it is possible that the errors in the forecasted values are due to this parameters that could not be included in the forecasting problem.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work the forecasting of the thermal power of FRESKO CSP with the application of ANN was investigated.

A previously developed ANN with 30 hidden neurons and 5 delays was used for forecasting the thermal power of FRESKO 24h ahead and good regression values were obtained from training, testing and validating the network. Alternative ANN structures were also investigated and it was concluded that for the considered forecasting problem a simple ANN structure with 10 hidden neurons and 2 delays can provide equally accurate results.

Forecasting errors are unavoidable though and these should be considered when applying the prediction in real conditions for

system management. It is highly possible that the errors are due to the parameter of dust that affects the system's production. Unfortunately, dust is not a parameter that can be measured.

The forecasting can be used for decision making in optimizing the system's operation and energy management. Forecasting the thermal power one day ahead will allow decision making regarding the charging and discharging of the thermal storage based on the forecasted thermal power production. A 24h horizon prediction can also be valuable in managing the hybrid solar installation of the company where there is both electrical and thermal power production.

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